

Functional Outcome of Management of Fracture Shaft of Humerus with Interlocking Nail**Gude Jayaram¹, Somu Sivakumar², Ramakanth Pechetty³, Amal PS⁴, I Rohith⁵, Ebel Raj N⁶**¹Associate Professor, Government Medical College, Kadapa²Assistant Professor, King George Hospital, Andhra Medical College, Vishakhapatnam³Assistant Professor, Rangaraya Medical College, Kakinada^{4,6}Senior Residents, ASRAM Medical College, Eluru⁵Civil Assistant Surgeon Orthopaedic Specialist, Area Hospital, Aganampudi, Visakhapatnam

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Abstract:

Introduction: The incidence of shaft humerus fractures remains 1% to 2% of all fractures and 14% of all humerus fractures. The gold standard of surgical management is open reduction and internal fixation with DCP. But it has complications like wound infections, iatrogenic radial nerve injury, and large scar which is a cosmetic concern for the patient. In the case of antegrade interlocking humerus nails, it is a biological preservative technique with union rates similar to that of DCP plate fixation.

Materials and Methods: Patients with fracture shaft of Humerus, who were admitted in Government General Hospital, attached to rangaraya Medical College, Kakinada was taken for study after obtaining their informed consent. This was a prospective study from December 2020 to December 2022.

Results: Majority of patients were Males between 31-40 years. RTA is the most common mode of injury (75%). The commonly seen injuries were transverse fractures of Middle 1/3rd of shaft of humerus. Majority (95%) patients had solid union in an average of 15.25 weeks, 90% of patients had full range of shoulder movements. Shoulder stiffness and superficial skin infections were the only complications encountered.

Discussion: 95% patients attained solid bony union within 15.25 weeks. 1 case (5%) went into non-union which was subjected to DCP fixation with bone graft at united at 32 weeks. When compared with plating, nailing had a least infection rate in postoperative period and minimal hospital stay. As the fracture site hematoma was preserved during surgery, the time required for the fracture consolidation and union would be less with higher union rates in nailing procedures.

Keywords: Fracture shaft of Humerus, Interlocking Nail.

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Introduction

The incidence of shaft humerus fractures remains 1% to 2% of all fractures and 14% of all humerus fractures [1]. The gold standard of surgical management is open reduction and internal fixation with DCP. But it has complications like wound infections, iatrogenic radial nerve injury, and large scar which is a cosmetic concern for the patient.

Even though minimally invasive techniques were brought into practice they do have all the complications of plate fixation. After the advent of the locking concept in the nailing procedure, we have had good results in the fixation of humerus shaft fractures. With a minimally invasive method in antegrade /retrograde manner of nail insertion and preservation of soft tissue, vascularity leads to better bone healing. Nailing is biomechanically good due to less subjectivity to bending and shearing forces.

Chances of cortical osteopenia and refracture are less after implant removal due to less stress shielding². In the case of antegrade interlocking humerus nails, it is a biological preservative technique with union rates similar to that of DCP plate fixation.

Materials and Methods

Patients with fracture shaft of Humerus, who were admitted in Government General Hospital, attached to rangaraya Medical College, Kakinada was taken for study after obtaining their informed consent.

This was a prospective study from December 2020 to December 2022. After taking their consent, they had been analysed clinically and radiologically. Proper history taking, evaluating the mode of injury

among all the selected patients was done before getting the, necessary clinical and laboratory investigations done in order to get fitness for surgery. We had selected 20 cases for this study and excluded patients aged less than 18 years and open fractures of Gustilo's type III. And we used interlocked nailing for stabilization of the fracture of the humerus.

We had to look for the distal radial pulse, capillary distal vascularity was assessed by radial artery pulsations, capillary refilling. We had to look for any parasthesia, motor or sensory deficit at wrist and hand in order to rule out any nerve injury by confirming the active flexion and extension at elbow, MCP joint and wrist. Standard radiography of the humerus, i.e, anteroposterior and lateral views, were obtained including one joint above and one joint below. The limb was immobilized in a U-Slab with sling. Injectable analgesics were given. The advantages of the surgery had to be explained to the patient and their attenders, informed consent was taken from them. All routine preoperative blood investigations were done.

Principles of Intramedullary Nail Fixation

Intramedullary nail in fixation of any shaft fracture gives a good mechanical support. It is a biological fixation which allows the patient to have an early mobilization of both soft tissue surrounding the fracture and joint as well. Both antegrade and retrograde nailing techniques are described for interlocked nailing in humerus shaft fractures. The displacement of a shaft fracture may vary at times in many ways. The fixation by an intramedullary nail in any such displaced fractures, the axial alignment and angulation would be restored. Most of the shaft fractures being simple type, locking of the intramedullary nail distally and proximally will give a good rotational stability. Interlocking of the nail prevents the telescoping within the bone and fragments in cases of multifragmented fractures, thereby providing longitudinal stability and preventing shortening.

Instrumentation

The nails conical proximal end has threads on the inner side which provides secure fixation of the threaded bolt for attaching insertion handle for the insertion and removal of the nail, positioning grooves precisely align the insertion handle with the nail and for fixation of the jig. The humeral diaphysis will admit a straight nail, but in an intramedullary nail it has a 5 degree bend proximally which gives a better alignment while inserting and removing the nail in both antegrade and retrograde method.

In cannulated and non-cannulated nails there are three holes in the proximal end lateral to medial and three in the distal end from which two are accessible

from anterior to posterior and one from lateral to medial. 6mm nail is non cannulated. 7mm & 8mm are cannulated. The proximal locking which accommodates 3.9mm locking except 6mm nail which accommodates 3.4mm locking screw. In the distal end there are 2 Anterior posterior locking and one lateral to medial and its diameter gives the nail a certain flexibility under bending and torsion which is necessary for fracture healing.

Patient Positioning: With the patient in supine /beach chair position, the head was turned towards the contralateral side and a sandbag in placed underneath the scapula. This extends the shoulder to expose the humeral head end during surgery and better exposure of the entry site. The whole arm segment is painted and draped. C-arm was positioned from the opposite of the fractured arm to prevent interference with maneuvering and easy handling of instrumentation. The surgeon is supposed to work from the head end during the surgery.

Approach and incision: 3cm incision was made from the lateral border of tip of the acromion extending distally. The deltoid muscle was split along its fibers. Care was taken not to extend the incision more than 3 to 4 cm to avoid injury to the axillary nerve. It is important to adduct the proximal humerus fragment which will assure adequate visualization of the rotator cuff before incision. The supraspinatus was incised along its fibers and tagged for adequate retraction and later suturing.

Entry point: Using a sharp bone awl, the entry point is made just 1-1.5 cm medial to the tip of the greater tuberosity at the junction of tuberosity and the head of the humerus, in line with the medullary canal. The position was confirmed with an image intensifier. The proximal fragment was adducted to make the entry point more convenient at marking the slope between the articular and non-articular surfaces looking under C-arm. When the fracture level was at a more proximal location the entry point was made more towards the articular surface/ medial entry was preferred. Advance the bone awl into the proximal humerus aiming slightly towards the medial cortex.

Insertion of the nail: The fracture was reduced intra-operatively and a guide pin was passed across the fracture site. According to the diameter of the medullary canal serial reaming was done with 6,7, and 8 mm reamers with the reduction maintained. The proper radiological measurements had to be taken preoperatively regarding size of the nail. But still intraoperatively reconfirmation was done again with the help of guide pin under c-arm guidance. The mounted nail was passed through the entry portal into the medullary canal by maintaining the convexity of the nail towards the medial cortex. Under C-arm guidance the fracture reduction was maintained and nail was advanced through both the

proximal and distal fragments over the guide pin till 2 cm proximal to olecranon fossa. The nail should be pushed deep so that its proximal end does not protrude out into the subacromial space. It is advised to deduct the nail length by 2cm both proximally and distally from the estimated nail length to avoid inadvertent proximal tip prominence and rotator cuff impingement.

Distal locking: Once the nail was advanced till the distal fragment, locking was done in AP screw hole of the nail. It was performed by free hand technique by giving a 2 cm incision and gentle soft tissue dissection was carried out. The soft tissue and biceps brachii muscle was split by blunt dissection, care was taken by tagging the muscle on either side which helps in better retraction. Thereby taking care not to injure the brachial artery and the median nerve. Under c-arm distal hole was visualized, the position of arm and jig checked. Distal hole is drilled with a tissue sleeve of 3.2 mm size for 7mm, 8mm nail and with 2.7 mm sleeve for 6mm nail. Distal locking was done with 3.4mm screw for 7mm, 8mm nail and with 2.9mm screw for 6mm nail. Once the distal screw was placed an axial load was applied proximally and distally in order to achieve better compression at fracture site. Or else the jig was back slapped to achieve compression.

Proximal locking: The proximal locking was from lateral to medial with the jig.

Careful drilling of proximal screw holes was to be done as any medial advancement would lead to neurovascular injury. Care is to be taken to avoid protrusion of the nail from the entry point proximally by selecting a shorter nail or a nail of adequate length.

Post-operative protocol: The patient's arm was immobilized with an arm pouch. Postoperatively the patients were asked to make fingers and wrist joint movements. The dressing was changed on the 2nd and 5th postoperative day. Unless the patients had any signs of infection or other complaints they had to be discharged on the 6th post-operative day i.e after 5 days of IV antibiotics with support of the arm pouch continued. All patients were advised to perform pendular movements at shoulder. They were strictly instructed not to lift any heavy weights or any works that put additional stress on the affected limb. Sutures/staples removal was done on 12th postoperative day. All the patients were reviewed up at 6 weeks, 3, 6, 12 months or till

fracture union & later at 6 monthly intervals till the completion of study.

They were examined in detail clinically and special stress was laid on shoulder and elbow range of movements and subjective complaints. X-rays were obtained in AP and lateral views and signs of union were looked for. The fracture was considered to be radio logically united, when there was no visible fracture line and evidence of callus bridging the fracture site. The functional outcome were assessed by modified Rommens et al criteria³. Based on the observed results grading was given as excellent, moderate, poor for all the patients. Loss of residual abduction was too looked among all patients along with few complaints such as pain which are subjective.

Results

In this series (15%) patients were between 20-30 years, 6(30%) patients were between 31-40 years, 4 (20%) patients were between 41-50 years, 4 (20%) patients were between 51-60 years, 3(15%) patient was between 61- 70 year. 13 (65%) patients were males and 7(35%) patients were females. RTA is the most common mode of injury i.e. 15(75%) patients out of 20. In this study polytrauma patients also had fractures of shaft humerus. The common level of injury was Middle 1/3rd a total of 13 (65%) patients, upper 1/3rd- middle 1/3rd junction - 3(15%) and middle 1/3rd-lower 1/3rd was 4 (20%) where transverse fracture pattern was seen in 13 (65%) patients, Oblique fracture pattern was seen 6 (30%) patients and segmental fracture in 1 (5%) patients. In our study, it was found that 18 patients (90%) had full range of shoulder movements. 1 (5%) patient had loss of residual 10 degree of abduction. 2 patients (10%) had > 20 degree loss of residual abduction. ROM was assessed by the ROMMENS et al grading.

During follow up 19 (95%) patients had solid union in an average of 15.25 weeks and 1 case of non-union (at 36 weeks), which was treated with bone grafting and plate fixation later. In this study 15 patients (75%) had no complications. 2(10%) cases had shoulder stiffness which was the most common complication and 1 (5%) case had superficial skin infection. Only 1(5%) case had Non-union. Another 1(5%) case had radial nerve injury which showed signs of recovery after 3 months of active physiotherapy.

Figure 1:

Discussion

Fractures of the shaft of the humerus were seen commonly in middle-aged adults ranging from 20-70yrs group, with the mean age being 43.45yrs, which was comparable with past and peer studies [4,5]. Male patients were injured more when compared to females as was seen in other studies as well may due to the work and daily activity which is more in males. In some of the females osteoporosis was a reason for these fractures. In the study, the most common cause of humerus fracture was RTA-15 cases (75%), and the 2nd most common cause was fall from height -2 cases (10%). As seen in other studies we also had RTA as the common mode of injury for these fractures [6,7]. In the present study, 13 cases (65%) were transverse fractures, The second most common type of fracture was oblique fracture -6 cases (30%). and 1 segmental fractures (5%). In the other studies as well, transverse types of humeral shaft fractures were seen more commonly [8,9] (45%) patients in this study had other associated injuries. Out of 20 cases 2 patients had associated rib fractures, 2 patients had associated ipsilateral distal radius fractures and 1 patient had associated intertrochanteric fractures, 1 patient had associated femoral shaft fractures, 2 patients had associated clavicle fracture, 1 patient had associated head injury and 11 patients were not associated with any injury. In the present study,

postoperatively 18 patients (90%) got the full range of shoulder movements (130 – 140 degrees of abduction). 2 patients had 30 degree loss of residual abduction that gradually lowered their functional outcome. Both of these patients underwent physiotherapy and recovered almost near full range of movement's later. 19 patients (95%) attained solid bony union within 15.25 weeks. 1 case (5%) went into non-union. This was a case of transverse fracture at the upper 1/3rd shaft which got comminuted intra- operatively. At 16 weeks follow up, since there were no signs of fracture union, the fracture site was opened and fixed with DCP and augmented with iliac bone graft. It got eventually united around 36 weeks.

The union rates were comparable to other studies [9]. In this study 2 patients (10%) had shoulder stiffness likely due to impingement of the proximal nail tip to rotator cuff tendons. Both of these patients had abduction less than 110 degrees in the immediate post-operative period. Both of them underwent rigorous physiotherapy with shoulder exercises and eventually got near full ROM. Transient radial nerve palsy was seen in one (5%) patient. This was a case of segmental fracture of humerus which developed radial nerve palsy in the immediate post-operative period. It was managed with dynamic cock-up splint and slowly recovered completely in 6 weeks.

Table 1: Comparison of union rates

Study	No. of patients	Management	Delayed Union	Nonunion	Overall Union
Bell M.J. et al	38	AO Plating	--	1(3%)	33(97%)
Rommens et al	39	IM Nailing	--	1	38(95%)
Jinn Lin et al	48	IM Nailing	--	--	100%
McCormack RG et al	44	IM nailing	--	3(12%)	41(88%)
Mir Wali et al	50	IM Nailing	5 (10%)	4 (8%)	48 (92%)
PRESENT STUDY	20	IM Nailing	---	1 (5%)	19(95%)

Conclusion

Most of the findings in the present study including union rates, complications, and functional results were comparable with other studies where intramedullary nailing was used in management of humeral shaft fractures.

This technique avoids extensive soft tissue dissection and subsequent fibrosis. The elasticity of the muscle tissue was also preserved. Also, the surgical site with a small scar would not be of much cosmetic concern. It allows an early mobilization of shoulder and elbow joints. One of the shortcomings of this study is that sample group was small, and needs to be conducted in a larger group of patients with longer follow up periods.

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